

IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF LAMBDA-CYHALOTHRIN ON SERUM PHOSPHOLIPIDS AND LIPOPROTEIN OF *RATTUS NORVEGICUS*

Dinesh C. Sharma

Department of Zoology, Faculty of Science, K. M. Govt. Girls P.G. College, Badalpur, G.B. Nagar - 203 027, India.
e-mail : dr_dineshsharma@hotmail.com

(Accepted 7 December 2017)

ABSTRACT : Synthetic pyrethroids are biological, physical and chemical agents used to kill organisms, which are harmful to human beings. Pesticides might be incorporated into plant tissue and food grains and as a result of this they enter into food chain and accumulate at various tropic levels after each generation through biomagnifications. Such pesticides are a menace, in a sense that they get entry into the mammalian body and cause alterations in various cytological, biochemical and physiological processes leading to serious complications.

The use of pyrethroids is increasing, because of their low mammalian toxicity but high insecticidal activity. The application of pyrethroids, which is often carried out without adequate expert knowledge, may lead to high pesticide residues, often combined with health hazards for the people concerned. Objective of the present study is to evaluate the impact of Cyno-group pyrethroid (lambda-cyhalothrin) on Phospholipids and Lipoprotein of *Rattus norvegicus*. The present study is aimed to observe the possible effect of the experimental pyrethroid on albino rats as they are easily reared in laboratory conditions and their resemblance to higher mammalian groups with regard to their physiology cannot be denied. In the present investigation serum phospholipids have been found to be significantly increased in both acute and sub-acute treatments after λ -cyhalothrin intoxication, while in recovery studies the increase has been found to be non-significant. The increase of LDL and HDL in the present study (*vide infra*) may also be responsible for increased serum phospholipids. Serum VLDL has been found to be increased significantly after acute and sub-acute treatments of λ -cyhalothrin in present investigation, while in recovery studies has been found to be non-significant.

Key words : λ -cyhalothrin (LCT), phospholipids, lipoproteins, LDL, HDL, VLDL albino rat.

INTRODUCTION

The rise of human population has crossed all strides in the beginning of 20th century with the result scientists had to employ all tactics to feed the rising population. During this course, some of the synthesized chemicals not only helped the mankind but also became reasons for his agony. A good number of chemicals in form of pesticides reigned for quite some time, however left many problems that were related to welfare of human beings.

It became essential to look for newer avenues to minimize the misery and plight of human population. To overcome the problem of food requirement, biologically safe pyrethroids are in vogue. However, their indiscriminate use is not free of problems. Unfortunately pesticides have diverse effects on the specific target species. Undesirable side effects are wide spread and include injury to non-target organisms, ecosystem imbalance and environmental contamination by persistent pesticides. Pesticides are biological, physical and chemical agents used to kill organisms, which are harmful to human beings.

In this situation, few chemicals were synthesized which were identical to natural origins. The pyrethroids were such in this series. The pyrethroids are grouped into two categories, one, type-I pyrethroid and the other type-II pyrethroid. LCT is a newer third generation type-II synthetic pyrethroid contains λ -cyno group and is available in a number of formulations (Meister, 1992). Due to its rapid metabolism and excretion its toxicity for mammal at present is quite low, however it may create problems in non-target species in future, if applied indiscriminately.

The investigation was carried out on the blood because it maintains the inner homeostatic mechanism and transport nutrients, metabolites, electrolytes, hormones, toxicants etc. in the body. Any change in blood composition reflects the abnormality of animal body. In the present study serum is used to study biochemical alterations, the phospholipids and lipoproteins (VLDL, LDL and HDL).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Test Compound

For the present study λ -cyhalothrin (LCT), a non-systemic pyrethroid insecticide with the trade name 'Karate' (CAS no. 91465-08-06), chemical name (R + S)-F-cyano-3-(phenoxyphenyl) methyl-(1S+1R)-cis-3-(2-chloro-3,3,3-trifluoroprop-1-enyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane-carboxylate of 98% purity, with contact and stomach action and repellent properties was procured from Zeneca-ICI Agro Chemicals, Chennai (India).

Maintenance and feeding of experimental albino rats

The experimental albino rats [*Rattus norvegicus* (Berkenhout)], procured from inbred colony were acclimated for one month to the laboratory conditions (temperature. $25^{\circ}\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$, relative humidity $60\pm 5\%$ and photoperiod 12 hr/day) before using them for the experiment. Adult male and female rats of almost equal size and weight were kept in the polypropylene cages and cleaned regularly to avoid any infection or undesirable odour in the laboratory. Each cage was equipped with a metallic food plate and water bottle. The albino rats were offered fresh feed daily throughout the experimentation on Gold Mohar rat and mice feed, manufactured by Hindustan Lever Ltd., India at regular interval and water was provided *ad libitum*.

Random selection of individuals

In the present study, for LD_{50} the data were analyzed statistically by log dose/probit regression line method (Finney, 1971). Oral LD_{50} of male and female rats was found to be 75.85-mg/kg body weight and 56.695-mg/kg body weight respectively (Saxena and Sharma, 2002; Sharma, 2004). The percent mortality response in the two sexes as per table 1 did not reveal any significant change ($p>0.05$). Hence, it could be possible to select the individuals randomly (irrespective of sex) for experimentation.

Five healthy adult albino rats (7–8 weeks of age, with average body weight of 150–200 g) were selected randomly for test, control and recovery studies sacrificed after 1, 2, 15, 30 and 45 (recovery) days for the collection of blood in the present investigation. Each rat was assigned a number for convenience prior to experimentation. All the rats of the experimental sets were given doses of LCT orally with the help of gavage tube and those of control sets equal amount of vehicle i.e. ground nut oil.

Selection of dose

Test agent : An oral dose of 18 mg/kg body weight for acute treatment, while for sub acute treatment 1/30

of acute dose was given for 30 days i.e. 0.6 mg/kg body weight/day by gavage tube. The recovery group did not receive any dose after 30 days of sub acute treatment till day 45.

Biochemical studies

Five rats from each set (control set and experimental sets) were sacrificed after 1, 2, 15, 30 and 45 (recovery) days for the collection of blood for the biochemical studies. All the rats of the experimental sets were given doses of λ -cyhalothrin orally with the help of gavage tube and those of control sets equal amount of vehicle i.e. ground nut oil.

Collection of blood samples

The rats were anaesthetized with chloroform and were placed in dissecting tray with their ventral side upwards. The blood samples were obtained with the help of 5.0 ml disposable syringe, fitted with the hypodermic needle (22 swg) directly from the ventricle of the heart of the dissected albino rats. The collected blood was transferred immediately into plain sterilized centrifuge tubes for the separation of serum.

Separation of serum

The centrifuge tubes containing blood samples were allowed to stand in standing position for about one hour at room temperature and were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 30 minutes. The supernatant serum was then carefully transferred to sterilized plain glass vials with the help of fine glass dropper for the estimation of Lipoproteins i.e. very low density lipoprotein (VLDL), low density lipoprotein (LDL) and high density lipoprotein (HDL).

Estimation of serum phospholipids and lipoproteins

Estimation of serum phospholipids

Phospholipids, the esters of glycerol containing two fatty acyl groups and phospholipid acids was estimated by Connerty *et al* (1961).

Principle-Proteins are precipitated by trichloroacetic acid. The precipitate contains the phospholipid. Metol digest an aliquot of the extract with sulphuric acid and hydrogen peroxide to oxidize the phosphorus to inorganic phosphate. The phosphate is liberated, which is determined colorimetrically.

Estimation of high-density lipoproteins (HDL)

HDL is a small particle constituting about 50% protein (mostly apoA-I and apoA-II and some apoC and apoE). 20% cholesterol, 30% phospholipid and only traces of triglyceride. HDL was estimated by the Wybenga and Pileggi method (1970)

Principle-High Density Lipoproteins (HDL) are

obtained in the supernatant after centrifugation. The cholesterol in the HDL fraction is also estimated by this method using SPAN diagnostic kit (code no 25924).

Calculations-

$$\text{Serum HDL (mg/dl)} = \frac{\text{OD of 'Test'}}{\text{OD of 'Standard'}} \times 50$$

Estimation of serum low density lipoproteins (LDL)

Low-density lipoproteins (LDL) constitute about 50% of the total lipoproteins mass in plasma. Cholesterol constitutes 50% of it, while proteins are 25% (mostly apoB-100 with traces of apoC). LDL was calculated from the values of Cholesterol, Very Low Density Lipoproteins and High Density Lipoproteins by using following formula given by Friedewald (1972).

$$\text{LDL} = \text{CHO} - (\text{VLDL} + \text{HDL})$$

Estimation of very low-density lipoproteins (VLDL)

Very low-density lipoproteins (VLDL) are rich in triglycerides. They have a lower lipid: protein ratio, and thus float at a somewhat higher density. An excessive amount of VLDL provides turbidity to plasma. VLDL triglycerides are of endogenous, mainly hepatic origin and constitute 50% VLDL. Cholesterol and phospholipid make up about 40% of the particle and about 10% of the mass is protein (mostly apo-B-100 and apo-C and some extect apoE). Very low-density lipoprotein was calculated by following formula given by DeLong (1986).

$$\text{VLDL} = \frac{\text{TG}}{6.5}$$

Statistical analysis

The data are compared by 't' test and expressed as mean±SE.

RESULTS

Serum phospholipids

(i) After 1 day acute treatment

The mean value of phospholipid in the serum of treated rats is 141.12 ± 0.99 mg/dl., whereas in the serum of control rats it is 133.41 ± 1.02 mg/dl.

A highly significant ($P < 0.01$) increase in the phospholipid content has been observed after two days of acute treatment as compared to control rats (Table 1, Fig. 1).

(ii) After 2 days acute treatment

The mean value of phospholipid in the serum of treated rats is 143.30 ± 0.96 mg/dl., whereas in the serum of

control it is 134.22 ± 0.95 mg/dl.

A highly significant ($P < 0.01$) increase in the phospholipid content has been observed after two days of acute treatment as compared to control rats (Table 1, Fig. 1).

(iii) After 15 days sub-acute treatment

The mean value of phospholipid in the serum of treated rats is 145.80 ± 0.87 mg/dl., whereas in the serum of control rats it is 134.92 ± 1.12 mg/dl.

A significant increase ($P < 0.01$) in the phospholipid content has been observed after fifteen days of sub acute treatment as compared to control rats (Table 1, Fig. 1).

(iv) After 30 days sub-acute treatment

The mean value of phospholipid in the serum of treated rats is 142.24 ± 1.19 mg/dl., whereas in the serum of control rats it is 131.56 ± 0.87 mg/dl.

A highly significant ($P < 0.01$) increase in the phospholipid content has been observed after thirty days of sub acute treatment as compared to control rats (Table 1, Fig. 1).

(v) Recovery group (45 days)

The mean value of phospholipid in the serum of treated rats is 137.19 ± 1.06 mg/dl., whereas in the serum of control it is 133.63 ± 1.01 mg/dl.

A non significant ($P > 0.05$) increase in the phospholipid content has been observed in recovery studies as compared to control rats (Table 1, Fig. 1).

Serum high density lipoprotein (HDL)

(i) After 1 day acute treatment

The mean value of HDL in the serum of treated rats is 29.08 ± 0.63 mg/dl., whereas in the serum of control it is 19.08 ± 0.86 mg/dl.

A highly significant ($P < 0.001$) increase in the HDL content has been observed after one day of acute treatment as compared to control rats (Table 2, Fig. 2).

(ii) After 2 days acute treatment

The mean value of HDL in the serum of treated rats is 31.20 ± 0.86 mg/dl., whereas in the serum of control rats it is 20.29 ± 0.41 mg/dl.

A highly significant ($P < 0.001$) increase in the HDL content has been observed after two days of acute treatment as compared to control rats (Table 2, Fig. 2).

(iii) After 15 days sub-acute treatment

The mean value of HDL in the serum of treated rats is 24.23 ± 0.92 mg/dl., whereas in the serum of control it is 20.90 ± 0.63 mg/dl.

Table 1 : Phospholipid estimation in serum of albino rats after acute, sub-acute λ -cyhalothrin intoxication and recovery.

S. No.	Treatment	Dose (mg/kg b. w.)	No. of individuals treated	Treatment time (in days)	Phospholipid level in serum (mg/dl)		Significance level
					Range	Mean \pm S.E.	
1.	Control*		5	01	131.72-137.24	133.41 \pm 1.02	\uparrow P < 0.01 HS
2.	Acute	18	5	01	140.31-144.73	141.12 \pm 0.99	
3.	Control*		5	02	132.26-135.60	134.22 \pm 0.95	\uparrow P < 0.01 HS
4.	Acute ³	18	5	02	142.32-145.73	143.30 \pm 0.96	
5.	Control*		5	15	133.80-136.11	134.92 \pm 1.12	\uparrow P < 0.01 HS
6.	Sub-acute	0.6	5	15	143.62-145.82	145.08 \pm 0.87	
7.	Control*		5	30	130.21-134.53	131.56 \pm 0.87	\uparrow P < 0.01 HS
8.	Sub-acute	0.6	5	30	141.62-146.96	142.24 \pm 1.19	
9.	Control*		5	45	131.61-136.20	133.63 \pm 1.01	\uparrow P > 0.05 NS
10.	Recovery ⁾	00	5	45	136.22-139.91	137.19 \pm 1.06	

Table 2 : High density lipoproteins (HDL) estimation in serum of albino rats after acute, sub-acute λ -cyhalothrin intoxication and recovery.

S. No.	Treatment	Dose (mg/kg b. w.)	No. of individuals treated	Treatment time (in days)	HDL level in serum (mg/dl)		Significance level
					Range	Mean \pm S.E.	
1.	Control*		5	01	16.66-21.21	19.09 \pm 0.86	\uparrow P < 0.001 VHS
2.	Acute	18	5	01	27.27-30.30	29.08 \pm 0.63	
3.	Control*		5	02	19.69-21.21	20.29 \pm 0.41	\uparrow P < 0.001 VHS
4.	Acute ³	18	5	02	28.78-33.33	31.20 \pm 0.86	
5.	Control*		5	15	19.69-22.72	20.90 \pm 0.63	\uparrow P < 0.05 SIG
6.	Sub-acute	0.6	5	15	22.72-27.27	24.23 \pm 0.92	
7.	Control*		5	30	19.69-22.72	21.51 \pm 0.63	\uparrow P < 0.01 HS
8.	Sub-acute	0.6	5	30	25.75-30.30	28.17 \pm 0.86	
9.	Control*		5	45	19.69-22.72	21.20 \pm 0.75	\uparrow P < 0.01 HS
10.	Recovery ⁾	00	5	45	24.24-27.27	26.05 \pm 0.63	

³ = Dose was given once and effect was observed after 48 hours.

) = Recovery assessment was carried out for 15 days soon after 30 days sub acute treatment.

\uparrow / \downarrow = Increase, Decrease

S.E. = Standard Error

* = Control were given the same quantity of diluents (Ground nut oil)

NS,HS = Non significant, Highly significant.

A significant increase (P < 0.05) in the HDL content has been observed after fifteen days of sub acute treatment as compared to control rats (Table 2, Fig. 2).

(iv) After 30 days sub-acute treatment

The mean value of HDL in the serum of treated rats is 28.17 \pm 0.86 mg/dl., whereas in the serum of control it is 21.51 \pm 0.63 mg/dl.

A highly significant (P < 0.01) increase in the HDL content has been observed after thirty days of sub acute treatment as compared to control rats (Table 2, Fig. 2).

(v) Recovery group (45 days)

The mean value of HDL in the serum of treated rats is 26.05 \pm 0.63 mg/dl., whereas in the serum of control it is 21.20 \pm 0.75 mg/dl.

A highly significant (P < 0.01) increase in the HDL content has been observed in recovery studies as

compared to control rats (Table 2, Fig. 2).

Serum low density lipoprotein (LDL)

(i) After 1 day acute treatment

The mean value of LDL in the serum of treated rats is 113.83 \pm 6.06 mg/dl., whereas in the serum of control it is 92.99 \pm 4.66 mg/dl.

A non significant (P > 0.05) increase in the LDL content has been observed after one day of acute treatment as compared to control rats (Table 3, Fig. 3).

(ii) After 2 days acute treatment

The mean value of LDL in the serum of treated rats is 204.82 \pm 8.41 mg/dl., whereas in the serum of control rats it is 101.79 \pm 6.99 mg/dl.

A significant (P < 0.001) increase in the LDL content has been observed after two days of acute treatment as compared to control rats (Table 3, Fig. 3).

Fig. 1 : Phospholipid estimation in serum of albino rats after acute, sub-acute λ -cyhalothrin intoxication and recovery.

Fig. 2 : HDL estimation in serum of albino rats after acute, sub-acute λ -cyhalothrin intoxication and recovery.

Fig. 3 : LDL estimation in serum of albino rats after acute, sub-acute λ -cyhalothrin intoxication and recovery.

Fig. 4 : VLDL estimation in serum of albino rats after acute, sub-acute λ -cyhalothrin intoxication and recovery.

(iii) After 15 days sub-acute treatment

The mean value of LDL in the serum of treated rats is 158.39 ± 4.09 mg/dl., whereas in the serum of controls is 103.18 ± 6.68 mg/dl.

A significant increase ($P < 0.01$) in the LDL content has been observed after fifteen days of sub acute treatment as compared to control rats (Table 3, Fig. 3).

(iv) After 30 days sub-acute treatment

The mean value of LDL in the serum of treated rats is 191.69 ± 4.03 mg/dl., whereas in the serum of control it is 108.68 ± 6.26 mg/dl.

A significant ($P < 0.001$) increase in the LDL content has been observed after thirty days of sub acute treatment as compared to control rats (Table 3, Fig. 3).

(v) Recovery group (45 days)

The mean value of LDL in the serum of treated rats is 106.60 ± 5.61 mg/dl., whereas in the serum of control rats it is 97.46 ± 6.54 mg/dl.

A non significant ($P > 0.05$) increase in the LDL content has been observed in recovery groups as compared to control rats (Table 3, Fig. 3).

Serum very low density lipoprotein (VLDL)

(i) After 1 day acute treatment

The mean value of VLDL in the serum of treated rats is 8.49 ± 1.20 mg/dl., whereas in the serum of control it is 7.90 ± 0.83 mg/dl.

A non significant ($P > 0.05$) increase in the VLDL content has been observed after one day of acute treatment as compared to control rats (Table 4, Fig. 4).

(ii) After 2 days acute treatment

The mean value of VLDL in the serum of treated rats is 9.72 ± 0.85 mg/dl., whereas in the serum of control rats it is 6.44 ± 0.83 mg/dl.

A significant ($P < 0.05$) increase in the VLDL content has been observed after two days of acute treatment as compared to control rats (Table 4, Fig. 4).

(iii) After 15 days sub-acute treatment

The mean value of VLDL in the serum of treated rats is 8.78 ± 0.89 mg/dl., whereas in the serum of controls it is 7.32 ± 0.73 mg/dl.

A non significant ($P > 0.05$) increase in the VLDL content has been observed after fifteen days of sub acute treatment as compared to control rats (Table 4, Fig. 4).

(iv) After 30 days sub-acute treatment

The mean value of VLDL in the serum of treated rats is 8.78 ± 0.89 mg/dl., whereas in the serum of control

Table 3 : Low density lipoproteins (LDL) estimation in serum of albino rats after acute, sub-acute λ -cyhalothrin intoxication and recovery.

S. No.	Treatment	Dose (mg/kg b. w.)	No. of individuals treated	Treatment time (in days)	HDL level in serum (mg/dl)		Significance level
					Range	Mean \pm S.E.	
1.	Control*		5	01	084.33-104.57	092.99 \pm 4.66	\uparrow P > 0.05
2.	Acute	18	5	01	103.81-133.79	113.83 \pm 6.06	NS
3.	Control*		5	02	085.79-115.78	101.79 \pm 6.99	\uparrow P < 0.001
4.	Acute ³	18	5	02	184.98-218.09	204.82 \pm 8.41	VHS
5.	Control*		5	15	082.76-117.30	103.18 \pm 6.68	\uparrow P < 0.01
6.	Sub-acute	0.6	5	15	149.65-168.48	158.39 \pm 4.09	HS
7.	Control*		5	30	098.51-128.60	108.68 \pm 6.26	\uparrow P < 0.001
8.	Sub-acute	0.6	5	30	181.20-203.75	191.69 \pm 4.03	VHS
9.	Control*		5	45	085.69-117.30	097.46 \pm 6.54	\uparrow P > 0.05
10.	Recovery ⁾	00	5	45	093.97-122.59	106.60 \pm 5.61	NS

Table 4 : Very low density lipoproteins (VLDL) estimation in serum of albino rats after acute, sub-acute λ -cyhalothrin intoxication and recovery.

S. No.	Treatment	Dose (mg/kg b. w.)	No. of individuals treated	Treatment time (in days)	HDL level in serum (mg/dl)		Significance level
					Range	Mean \pm S.E.	
1.	Control*		5	01	5.86-10.25	7.90 \pm 0.83	\uparrow P > 0.05
2.	Acute	18	5	01	5.86-11.72	8.49 \pm 1.20	NS
3.	Control*		5	02	4.39-08.79	6.44 \pm 0.83	\uparrow P < 0.05
4.	Acute ³	18	5	02	7.32-11.72	9.72 \pm 0.85	SIG.
5.	Control*		5	15	5.86-08.79	7.32 \pm 0.73	\uparrow P > 0.05
6.	Sub-acute	0.6	5	15	5.86-10.25	8.78 \pm 0.89	NS
7.	Control*		5	30	4.39-08.79	7.02 \pm 0.80	\uparrow P > 0.05
8.	Sub-acute	0.6	5	30	7.32-11.72	8.78 \pm 0.89	NS
9.	Control*		5	45	5.86-08.79	7.03 \pm 0.61	\uparrow P > 0.05
10.	Recovery ⁾	00	5	45	4.39-08.79	7.32 \pm 0.89	NS

³ = Dose was given once and effect was observed after 48 hours.

) = Recovery assessment was carried out for 15 days soon after 30 days sub acute treatment.

\uparrow / \downarrow = Increase, Decrease

S.E. = Standard Error

* = Control were given the same quantity of diluents (Ground nut oil)

NS,HS = Non significant, Highly significant

it is 7.02 \pm 0.80 mg/dl.

A non significant (P > 0.05) increase in the VLDL content has been observed after thirty days of sub acute treatment as compared to control rats (Table 4, Fig. 4).

(v) Recovery group (45 days)

The mean value of VLDL in the serum of treated rats is 7.32 \pm 0.89 mg/dl., whereas in the serum of control rats it is 7.03 \pm 0.89 mg/dl.

A non significant (P > 0.05) increase in the VLDL content has been observed in recovery studies as compared to control rats (Table 4, Fig. 4).

DISCUSSION

Phospholipids are the esters of fatty acids with glycerol containing an esterified phosphoric acid and a nitrogenous base and are an important constituent of cell membrane because they contain both polar and non-polar

sections (amphipathic molecule). Their differing group allows the phospholipids to interact both with water (charged portion) and organic compounds (non-charged portion). Phospholipids provide the basic organizing features of membrane as permeability barriers, as two dimensional scaffolds for cellular and organellar forms, and as the hydrophobic milieu for membrane bound enzymes, such as those involved in electron transfer, energy transduction and the maintenance of chemical concentration gradients. Sharma and Saxena (2010, 2013), Sharma *et al* (2010, 2012) observed the genotoxic potential of lambda-cyhalothrin. Singh *et al* (2008) observed the biochemical effects of carbamate and fenvalrate. Saxena and Sharma (1999) observed the effect of hafen 20EC on brain cholesterol, glycogen and total lipid of albino rat. Saxena and Sharma (2000) also evaluate the effect of synthetic pyrethroid on behavior pattern in *Rattus norvegicus*.

In the present investigation, serum phospholipids have been found to be significantly increased in both acute and sub acute treatments after λ -cyhalothrin intoxication, while in recovery studies the increase has been found to be non-significant. Present findings gain support by the work of Vaittinen *et al* (1995) and Pandey (2001) who reported elevated serum phospholipids in rats after MX and cypermethrin intoxication, respectively.

Since phospholipids are actively degradable lipids (Harper *et al*, 1978), their rapid increase suggests their immediate utilization for providing energy through gluconeogenesis. The increase of serum phospholipids reflects the elevation in gluconeogenesis in liver, as observed after fenvalerate (a synthetic pyrethroid) intoxication in chickens (Majumdar *et al*, 1994). Similar mechanism may also be valid for elevated serum phospholipids under λ -cyhalothrin stress which is again a pyrethroid.

Since phospholipids are major component of plasma membrane, entry of toxicant damages the plasma membrane components like lipids, protein, and enzymes (Arunadevy *et al*, 1999). Membrane of erythrocytes is fully permeable to insecticides and therefore this is likely to result in destruction of erythrocytes (Mass and Hathway, 1964). Probably elevation in phospholipids under λ -cyhalothrin may result in damage of erythrocyte membrane to release membrane phospholipids, which lead to hyperphospholipidemia as observed in the present studies and is in accordance to Qadri *et al* (1987), who reported reduction in R.B.C. count after pyrethroid intoxication.

Ahmad *et al* (1989) and Adilaxamma and Reddy (1995) found decrease in serum cholinesterase activity in rats after cypermethrin and monocrotophos intoxication respectively, as a result of which acetylcholine gets accumulated in synapse and inhibits the formation of acetylcholine in neuron from acetyl CoA and choline. This choline, which is not used for acetylcholine biosynthesis, may be diverted for synthesis of phospholipids because choline is the precursor for phospholipid biosynthesis, as a result of this phospholipid level increase in serum. Similar mechanism may also be considered responsible for enhancement in phospholipids in the present study following λ -cyhalothrin intoxication.

The increase of LDL and HDL in the present study (*vide infra*) may also be responsible for increased serum phospholipids, because phospholipids constitutes about 25% of LDL mass and about 30% of HDL mass (Henry, 1991).

The non-significant increase of serum phospholipids in recovery group rats reveals quick detoxification of λ -

cyhalothrin on account of being a pyrethroid.

Lipid bound proteins, the so called lipoproteins are found in plasma and their function is to transport lipids. Without these proteins lipids cannot exist in dissolved state in the blood. These lipoproteins control cholesterol transport to the deposition site in the concerned cells. Of the three lipoproteins (VLDL, LDL and HDL), only VLDL is initially formed in liver (Guyton and Hall, 1996).

VLDL particles have lower lipid: protein ratio, and thus float at a somewhat higher density in blood. Their excessive amount as seen in the present investigation makes the plasma turbid. Further, VLDL being rich in triglycerides and poor in protein content yet its formation is mostly possible by cholesterol and phospholipids (Henry, 1991).

Serum VLDL has been found to be increased significantly after acute and sub-acute treatments of λ -cyhalothrin in present investigation, while in recovery studies has been found to be non-significant.

The observed low lipase activity (*vide infra*) may be considered responsible for higher serum VLDL level and is in affirmation to Reymer *et al* (1995) and Bey *et al* (2001) who demonstrated low lipase activity to be responsible for increase in VLDL. The concentration of VLDL depends upon triglycerides (DeLong, 1986). Thus elevated triglyceride (*vide supra*) is responsible for elevated serum VLDL concentration in plasma in the present study. Similarly the increase of phospholipids and cholesterol (*vide supra*) may also be considered responsible for higher VLDL.

LDL, a cause of atherosclerosis commonly known as 'bad cholesterol' and constitutes about 50% of the total lipoprotein mass of plasma. The LDL particles are much smaller than the triglyceride rich lipoproteins (VLDL). Cholesterol accounts for about half of LDL mass (about 25% of LDL mass is protein), while triglycerides account for 4-8% and phospholipids 18-24% in blood (Henry, 1991).

Serum LDL has been assessed to be increased significantly in both acute and sub-acute treatments of λ -cyhalothrin, as contrast to recovery studies. The increase in cholesterol (*vide supra*) supports the increase in serum LDL in the present study because LDL is rich in cholesterol (Henry, 1991).

HDL is generally present as small particles constituting about 50% protein, 20% cholesterol, 30% phospholipids and possesses only traces of triglycerides (Henry, 1991). In the present investigation, serum HDL has been found to be significantly increased after acute

and sub-acute treatments of λ -cyhalothrin and in recovery group.

Further, increase in phospholipids, cholesterol (*vide supra*) and protein support the increase of HDL in the present study. The low lipase activity is often associated with low HDL concentration (Shimada *et al*, 1995 and Reymer *et al*, 1995), However non-significant reduction in lipase may be responsible for increase in HDL.

REFERENCES

- Adilaxamma K and Reddy K S (1995) Effect of Monocrotophos on blood chemistry and serum enzymic profile in lactating rats. *Indian J. Toxicol.* **2**, 21-25.
- Arunadevy R, Jaya A, Suganthi O M A and Ramalingam V (1999) Effect of mercuric chloride on testicular lipid classes in adult albino rats. *Indian J. Toxicol.* **6**(2), 41-47.
- Bey L, Areiqat E, Sano A and Hamilton M T (2001) Reduced lipoprotein lipase activity in postural skeletal muscle during aging. *J. Appl. Physiol.* **91**(2), 687-92.
- Connerty H V, Briggs A R and Jr. Eaton E H (1961) Determination of phospholipid. *Clin. Chem.* **7**, 589.
- Delong D M, Delong E R, Wood P D, Lipple K and Rifkind B M (1986) A comparison of methods for the estimation of plasma low and very low-density lipoprotein cholesterol. *The lipid Res. Clinics Prevalence Study. JAMA* **256**, 2372.
- Finney D J (1971) *Probit analysis*. Cambridge University Press, 303.
- Friedewald W T, Levy R I and Fredrickson D S (1972) Estimation of the concentration of low-density lipoprotein cholesterol in plasma without use of the preparative Ultracentrifuge. *Clin. Chem.* **18**, 499.
- Guyton A C and Hall J E (1996) *Textbook of Medical Physiology* (9th ed.). Prism Books Pvt. Ltd., Bangalore, India.
- Harper H A, Rodwell V W and Mayes P A (1978) *Review of Physiological Chemistry*. 17th ed. Langer Medical Publications.
- Henry J B (1991) *Clinical and diagnosis management by laboratory methods* (18th ed). W. B. Saunders Comp. : 189-213.
- Majumdar S, Mandol T K, Bhattacharya A and Basak D K (1994) Subacute toxicity of fenvalrate in broiler chicks, concentration cytotoxicity and biochemical profiles. *Indian J. Exp. Biol.* **32**, 752-56.
- Mass J A and Hathway D E (1964) Transport of organic compounds in the mammalian partition of dieldrin and telodrin between the cellular components and soluble proteins of blood. *Biochem. J.* **91**, 384-93.
- Meister R T (1992) *Farm chemicals Handbook*. Mister Pub. Co. Willoughby, OH.
- Pandey S (2001) Effect of synthetic pyrethroid on certain hemato-biochemical parameters on *Rattus norvegicus*. *Ph.D. Thesis*. Deptt. of Zoology, Dr. B.R.A. University, Agra.
- Qadri S S H, Jabeen K, Mahboob M and Mustafa M (1987) Hematotoxicity to chicken (*Gallus gallus domesticus*) by technical and formulation grades of some
- Reymer P W, Gagne E, Groenemeyer B E, Zhang H, Forsyth I, Jansen H, Seidell J C, Kromhout D, Lie K E, Kastelein J and Hayden M R (1995) A lipoprotein lipase (Asn291Ser) is associated with reduced HDL cholesterol levels in premature atherosclerosis. *Nat. Genet.* **10**, 28-43.
- Shimada M, Ishibashi S, Takanari G, Kawamura M, Yamamoto K, Inaba T, Harada K, Ohsuga J, Perrey S, Yazaki Y and Nobuhiro Y (1995) Overexpression of human lipoprotein lipase protects diabetic transgenic mice from diabetic hypertriglyceridemia and hypercholesterolemia. *Arterioscler. Thromb.* **15**, 1688-94.
- Vaittinen S L, Komulainen H, Kosmas V M, Julkunen A, Maki J, Paakkanen, Jansson K, Vartiainen T and Tuomisto J (1995) Subchronic toxicity of 3-Chloro-4-(Dichloromethyl)-5-Hydroxy-2(5H)-Furnone (MX) in wistar rats. *Pd. Chem. Tox.* **33**(12), 1027-37.
- Wybenga D R and Pileggi (1970) *In vitro* determination of cholesterol and HDL cholesterol in serum/plasma. *Clin. Chem.* **16**, 980.
- Sharma Dinesh C and Saxena P N (2010) Assessment of DNA degradation in lymphocytes of albino rat under lambda-cyhalothrin stress. *World Applied Sciences J.* **11** (1), 24-28.
- Sharma Dinesh C, P N Saxena, V K Singh and Sharma R (2010) Assessment of Clastogenicity of λ -Cyhalothrin, A Synthetic Pyrethroid in Cultured Lymphocytes of Albino Rat. *World Applied Sciences J.* **8**, 1093-1099.
- Sharma Dinesh C and Saxena P N (2013) Evaluation of the genotoxic potential of Lambda cyhalothrin in cultured lymphocytes of *Rattus norvegicus* (Berkenhout). *World J. of Appl. Sci. and Res.* **3**(1), 09-14.
- Sharma Dinesh C, Saxena P N and Manoj K Mittal (2012) Impact assessment of Lamda-Cyhalothrin stress on DNA degradation in lymphocytes of *Rattus norvegicus*. *Indian Res J. Genet. Biotechnol.* **4** (2), 89-94.
- Singh S P, Chaudhary R, Gaur K K, Sharma D C and Yadav S (2008) Biochemical effect of chronic dose of carbamate and fenvalrate administered continuously for 60 days on liver and muscle of fresh water fish, *Channa punctatus* (Bloch.). *J. Ecophysiol. Occu. Health* **8**(1-2), 119-22.
- Saxena P N and Dinesh C Sharma (1999) Effect of hafen 20EC on brain cholesterol, glycogen and total lipid of albino rat. *Indian J. Enviorn. Toxicol.* **2**, 72-73.
- Saxena P N and Dinesh C Sharma (2000) Effect of synthetic pyrethroid on behavior pattern in *Rattus norvegicus*. *National Academy of Science, Allahabad. Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India* **70** (B), 41-43.
- Saxena P N and Dinesh C Sharma (2002) Role of Sex and route of administration in determining LD₅₀ of λ -Cyahalthrin in wistar rats. *India J. Enviorn. Toxicol.* **12**, 92-93.